

Holter telemonitoring system with data sending to the cloud

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Abstract — Cardiovascular diseases (CVD) have become the leading cause of death worldwide. The electrocardiogram (ECG) is one of the simplest and quickest tests used to immediately assess cardiovascular health, effectively recording the heart's electrical activity. However, in some situations, prolonged monitoring is necessary, making a conventional ECG insufficient. In these cases, a Holter monitor is used, a device capable of continuously recording cardiac activity for several hours. Due to logistical and infrastructure challenges in certain regions, tools such as telemedicine and telemonitoring are gaining ground and are proving promising alternatives, enabling the remote monitoring of physiological parameters through electronic devices connected to communication systems. Cloud storage systems are also emerging as application strategies for improving data access for healthcare professionals. The objective of this work was to develop a prototype for acquiring, processing, and visualizing ECG signals, integrated with Google Sheets for cloud-based monitoring. The prototype was able to capture the signal, which was later saved and converted into the appropriate formats for software processing and cloud transmission. Based on the results, it was possible to conclude that the device integrated into the system can provide a more affordable solution for cardiac monitoring.

Keywords— Cardiovascular diseases, electrocardiogram (ECG), Holter monitor, telemedicine, telemonitoring, arrhythmia detection.

I. INTRODUCTION

At the beginning of the 20th century, cardiovascular diseases (CVD) accounted for less than 10% of all deaths worldwide. By the end of the century, CVD accounted for nearly half of all deaths in the developed world and 25% in the developing world. This global increase in CVD results from a dramatic shift in the health status of individuals worldwide throughout the 20th century, largely due to improved nutrition and public health measures [1].

In Brazil, cardiovascular diseases are responsible for the largest number of deaths in the population, with twice as

many deaths caused by cancer, 2.3 times more than external causes (accidents and violence), 3 times more than respiratory diseases, and 6.5 times more than all infections, including AIDS. Every hour, approximately 46 people lose their lives due to some form of cardiovascular disease. Many of these deaths could be delayed, or even avoided, with preventive care and therapeutic measures [2].

In the context of heart disease, preventive care and therapeutic measures depend on early diagnosis and identification, factors that face obstacles for healthcare professionals. Among the causes that contribute to these obstacles are the variety of clinical presentations of heart disease, overlapping symptoms, and the lack of specificity of certain traditional diagnostic methods [3].

According to the Departamento de Informática do Sistema Único de Saúde (DATASUS), a unit of the Ministry of Health responsible for managing the information systems and technological infrastructure of the SUS, in 2023 (most recent data available on the website), 1,465,610 Brazilians died. Of this total, 388,177 (26.5%) deaths were the result of diseases of the circulatory system. Among the main diseases that led to this number, the following stand out: acute myocardial infarction (94,008), essential hypertension (34,354), stroke (NE as ischemic hemorrhagic) (33,759), heart failure (30,936), hypertensive heart disease (21,089), and chronic ischemic heart disease (20,453) [4].

The 20th century was marked by discoveries in the field of heart health research, particularly after the creation of the electrocardiograph in 1902, which provided medicine with a revolutionary tool capable of assisting medical professionals in the diagnosis of various heart diseases [5].

Holter monitors are proven effective tools for diagnosing and monitoring cardiac arrhythmias. While the ECG allows for the momentary assessment of cardiac activity, new Holter monitoring technologies and loop recorders allow for prolonged monitoring of heart rhythm for periods ranging from a few days to several months [6].

This test can detect atrial or ventricular arrhythmias that may occur even when asymptomatic, alerting the physician

to the condition and the feasibility of specific therapy. This can include prescribing antiarrhythmic or anticoagulant medications or even making decisions such as implanting a pacemaker or cardioverter defibrillator [6].

Given the need for continuous monitoring of cardiac activity for research purposes, this work proposes the development of a low-cost Holter monitoring prototype, combined with telemonitoring, as a viable and accessible alternative for patients and healthcare professionals.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The development of the proposed project, detailed in Fig. 1, was divided into the following main parts: the construction of simple hardware capable of collecting electrocardiogram signals, the implementation of a software system for processing the signals and sending them to the cloud, and the use of a database for more detailed analyses of cardiac activity behavior.

Fig. 1 Project block diagram.

For simple hardware assembly, the following components were used:

- AD8232 heart sensor;
- ESP32;
- Micro USB cable;
- Electrodes.

The strategy used was a modified three-lead electrocardiogram, based on Einthoven's triangle. This configuration allows the capture of cardiac activity signals, although it does not represent a conventional 12-lead electrocardiogram system [7].

In this configuration, as shown in Fig. 2, one electrode is positioned below the left clavicle, near the left arm (LA), a second electrode is positioned below the right clavicle, near the right arm (RA), and a third electrode is used as a reference (Ref), located on the right side of the abdomen. This configuration allows for simplified signal acquisition, ideal for portable systems or prototypes.

The sensor captures the signals, which are sent to the ESP-32. The files are then formatted, processed, and stored, then sent to Google Sheets and displayed. The information is sent to Google Sheets via a connection, where the information is sent in real time, and only those with access to the folder can access and view it.

Fig. 2 Block diagram of the project.

With the electrodes positioned and the device assembled, the raw ECG signal was acquired via a USB connection, using the Arduino integrated development environment (IDE) with C programming. The sampling frequency was 200 Hz, based on the Nyquist equation, described in (I).

The ECG signal components have frequencies primarily below 100 Hz. Therefore, according to the Nyquist Theorem, for adequate signal capture and to avoid aliasing, the sampling frequency must be at least twice the highest signal frequency.

$$f_s \geq 2 \times f_{\max} \quad (I)$$

Where:

f_s = sampling frequency (in Hz);

f_{\max} = highest frequency present in the original signal (in Hz).

Simultaneously, the data was sent to Visual Studio Code, where it was processed using Python scripts. The first step was to convert the recorded data into the formats required for analysis: .dat, .hea, and .atr.

In this format, .dat files contain raw ECG signal data, storing the digitized signal samples. .hea files contain information about the ECG signal, such as the number of channels, frequency, and number of samples. .atr files contain data on important events in the signal, such as abnormal beats and arrhythmias. Signal processing began

with the application of, respectively, high-pass, low-pass and a notch filter. For medical applications, the Butterworth filter is the better choice because it is computationally fast and almost as accurate. So, for all filters, it was used the digital Butterworth filter [8].

The 0.5 Hz high-pass filter, with 2 poles, attenuates frequencies below the threshold and primarily eliminates low-frequency components of the signal with moderate transition, which can be slow noise or motion artifacts. The 45 Hz low-pass filter, with 4 poles, primarily eliminates high-frequency components of the signal, which can be electrical noise or high-frequency artifacts. The 4 poles combination results in an efficient high frequency rejection. Finally, the 60 Hz notch filter, also with 2 poles was applied to attenuate the residual power line interference from the signal, with relatively narrow rejection width.

The ECG tracing, presented in Fig.3, consists of a wave cycle known as PQRST, a cycle that represents the heart's electrical activity during a beat.

Fig. 3: PQRST Waves in an ECG beat.

The P wave represents the depolarization of the atria, the electrical activation that leads to the contraction of the heart's upper chambers. The QRS waves represent the depolarization of the ventricles, the heart's lower chambers. Of these, the R peak is the highest and easiest to identify. And the T wave represents the repolarization of the ventricles [9].

It made it possible to calculate the heart's beats per minute (BPM), using a calculation, given in (II), based on the peaks of the heart's R wave, which, as mentioned in the previous paragraph, represents the most prominent peak. The calculation was made using the formula:

$$bpm = \frac{n^{\text{of R waves peaks in the window}}}{\text{window duration in seconds}} \times 60 \text{ (II)}$$

A database, the Long-Term ST Database [10], was used to analyze samples for long periods and as a basis for validating the signals captured by the hardware. The files contain 24-hour records of ECG signals and were also processed. The information was subsequently sent to the cloud.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The microcontroller is powered by the computer, sending a voltage of 3.3 V to the sensor, which receives the information captured by the electrodes and sends it back to the microcontroller through its output, connected to pin 34. Its schematic can be seen in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: schematic of the microcontroller connection to the sensor.

With the project assembled, the signal captured the USB connection enabled data transmission, so it was possible to proceed with data processing. The main objective was to find the BPM values from the database samples, as shown in Fig. 5, and upload them to the cloud, as demonstrated in Fig. 6.

Fig. 5: ECG signal after processing and BPM rate, both from database.

The system chosen for sending and storing the results was Google Sheets, where the spreadsheets are stored in the cloud, on Google Drive, in the same cloud format used by [11]. In this configuration, the data is displayed in real time and saved, allowing for sharing, ensuring easy accessibility for healthcare professionals who have access to the spreadsheet via a link from any device with an internet connection.

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	Patient_1	Minute	BPM	Patient_2	Minute	BPM
2	s20031	0	76	s20041	0	60
3	s20031	1	79	s20041	1	64
4	s20031	2	77	s20041	2	62
5	s20031	3	81	s20041	3	63
6	s20031	4	79	s20041	4	62
7	s20031	5	77	s20041	5	64
8	s20031	6	84	s20041	6	84
9	s20031	7	82	s20041	7	89
10	s20031	8	80	s20041	8	76
11	s20031	9	84	s20041	9	73
12	s20031	10	79	s20041	10	77
13	s20031	11	82	s20041	11	78
14	s20031	12	79	s20041	12	78

Fig. 6: BPM rate in a Google Sheets table.

In Fig. 6, when we look at the data of “Patient_1”, we can see the values showed in Fig. 5. Additionally, it was also possible to plot graphs with the real-time ECG waveforms, from both the database and the hardware signals.

The signals acquired by the hardware, illustrated in Fig. 7, closely matched the characteristics observed in the database signals in Fig. 5 [10], which allowed the identification of the R pole, making it possible to extract the heart rate despite originating from a simpler system. Nevertheless, estimating heart rate values still requires further refinement.

Fig.7: ECG signal from hardware after processing.

The filters were the main mechanisms responsible for attenuating noise and allowing the captured signal to be as faithful as possible to a classic ECG waveform. As is well known, the most relevant spectral components of the pure ECG signal must be above 0.5 Hz [8]. The frequency components that make up the ECG are within the following parameter: Heart rate: 0.67 – 5 Hz; P-wave: 0.67 – 5 Hz; QRS: 10 – 50 Hz; T-wave: 1 – 7 Hz.

The value of 0.5 Hz as the cutoff frequency of the high-pass filter is chosen mainly to remove very slow variations that are not part of the cardiac electrical activity and interfere with the analysis, without compromising components of the heartbeat [12]. This filter with this cutoff value was applied to our signal, attenuating the artifacts below the cutoff frequency in question.

One of the most common artifacts in ECGs is that resulting from muscle activity, which is concentrated between 5 and 50 Hz. To attenuate these components and movement artifacts, a cutoff frequency of 40 Hz is commonly used in low-pass filters [8]. Since the main frequency component of the ECG, the QRS complex, occurs mainly between 10 and 50 Hz, and based on the literature, a cutoff frequency of 45 Hz was applied to our signals, attenuating the artifacts as expected and preserving a greater portion of the signal.

For the last, 60 Hz interference can be a problem in any biopotential measurement situation. This interference comes from the potential of the power supply network, which is inevitably present in any situation. Interference caused by the power network at 60 Hz, both in Brazil and in the US, where the database was collected, can be difficult to detect visually in signals with irregular waveforms, such as ECGs. This interference can be attenuated using a digital notch filter [13], as performed in this study.

Despite being an experiment with a simple variation and having encountered some limitations such as noise and movement artifacts, the prototype managed to capture cardiac signals and the behavior of the waves reproduces the waveform characteristics of the signals in the database, making explicit the peak of the R wave, the main component evaluated in this work.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The prototype achieved the proposed objectives of acquiring, processing, and transmitting signals to a simple cloud-based system. It was possible to observe the ECG signal wave-form characteristics, the R peak, the beats per minute value, apply filters for better signal quality, and display them in real time.

Implementing a system capable of transmitting and storing data in an accessible, secure, and simple manner can be a way to improve access to healthcare in regions with limited

infrastructure and technology. Limitations such as the short recording time of the signals captured by the device (compared to the duration of the database files) and the presence of noise and artifacts of movements were evident in the results. We also emphasize that the device has no clinical employability. These are issues that will need to be addressed, as will the feasibility of its implementation in healthcare systems.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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